

**STUDY OF LOANWORDS IN THE NEWS MEDIA TEXTS IN THE
UZBEK AND KARAKALPAK LANGUAGES**

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Annotation: This article deals with the main issues related to the media linguistics and media new texts, particularly, the usage of the loanwords, especially, borrowed from the English language and there are given the real examples with their contexts taken from the local news sites. The etymology of these loanwords are analyzed with the formation of the words in the target languages.

Being the most reproducible and repeatable texts of the Internet media, news texts are influenced not only by sub-standard layers of the Russian spoken language, but also by different layers of vocabulary of other languages. The term "borrowing" is ambiguous. It denotes the result of contacts of multilingual people and the process of transferring elements from one language to another [1, 24] In addition, foreign words are called borrowing. And finally, borrowing denotes both the process and the words. In both uzbek and karakalpak linguistics, there are the following problems regarding borrowings: which word should be considered a borrowing; the reasons for borrowing; varieties of foreign-language units; ways of mastering a word in a borrowing language; exactly what are calques and others.

Defining the types of foreign-language words, L. P. Krysin identifies borrowed words, exotic vocabulary and foreign-language inclusions [1, 57,58].

Having analyzed uzbek headlines of online publications "Kun.uz", "daryo.uz", "UzA.uz", "qalampir.uz" , we investigated the borrowed words found in them (in fifteen news texts). In order to determine their variety, it is necessary to analyze their lexical

meaning, origin and functions of the selected lexemes: “LG kompaniyasi **smartfon** ishlab chiqarishni to’xtatdi” (daryo.uz); “O’zbekistonda **krossover** mashinaraining narxlari elon qilindi” (xabar.uz); “Kevin Mitnik yana bir **xaker** – Lenni Di Chikko bilan hamkorlikda ishlay boshladi..... bu voqea shunchaki **xakerlar** o’g’irlangan pulni bo’lisha olmagani ortidan kelib chiqqan degan versiyani ilgari surdi” (daryo.uz); “Endi Agrobank tizimidagi xabarlarni telegram, **Instagram** va facebookda kuzatib borishingiz mumkun” (kun.uz); “Mirziyonomika kitobi **plagiat** mahsuli ekanligi aytilganida, Kitob muallifi Behruz Hamzayev Kun.uz’ga bergan intervyusida “Mirziyonomika”ni yozishda Rossiya nashri va boshqa manbalardan foydalanganini tan oldi, biroq bu **plagiat** hisoblanmasligini ta’kidladi (kun.uz); “Samarqand viloyatida **repperlar** janjali yuzasidan ish qo’zg’atildi” (qalampir.uz); “Yosh matbuotchi va **blogerlar** taqdirlandi” (UzA.uz); “«Word» matnli hujjat ko’rinishidagi kompyuter **virusi** paydo bo’ldi”(xabar.uz)

And from karakalpak headlines of online publications such as “Karinform.uz”, “kruz.uz”, “Kar24.uz”:

«**Смартфонның** қасына банк картасын қойыў қәуипли ме? Қәнигелер не дейди?» (karinform.uz); «**Кроссовер** машиналарының имканиятлары ҳаққында билип алың» (karinform.uz); «Өзбекстан сайтларына неше мәрте **хакерлик** хужимлер болғаны мәлим етилди» (karinform.uz); «Өзбекстандағы текстли **плагиатларды** анықлаў ушын ислеп шығылған биринши система ҳаққында билесиз бе?» (karinform.uz); «Мәлимлеме ҳәм ғалабалық коммуникациялар агентлиги директоры Комил Алламжонов **Инстаграмдағы** өз бетинде рәсмий баянат жасады» (karinform.uz); «Комментарий қалдырған пайдаланыўшылардың 56 проценти өз **аккаунтына** кире алмай атырғанын билдирген» (karinform.uz); «**Реппер** болған уақыя бойынша рәсмий баянат жасады» (Kar24.uz); «Ардақлаўда жылдың ең жақсы **блогери** анықланды» (karinform.uz); «Телеграмда тарқалған вирус ҳаққында мағлыўмат берилди» (karinform.uz).

Now the lexical meanings and the origin of the 15 selected words that found in the news texts will be analyzed.

Krossover – eng. Crossover - In engineering is a device that divides the frequency spectrum of a signal into two or more parts. English Crossover

(dictionary.cambridge.org). From cross over — cross-country driving. Type of all-terrain vehicle;

Plagiat – eng. Plagiarism - "the purloining or wrongful appropriation of another's ideas, writing, artistic designs, etc., and giving them forth as one's own," 1620s, from -ism + plagiary (n.) "plagiarist, literary thief" (c. 1600), from Latin plagiarius "kidnapper, seducer, plunderer, one who kidnaps the child or slave of another," used by Martial in the sense of "literary thief," from plagiare "to kidnap," plagium "kidnapping," from plaga "snare, hunting net" (also "open expanse, territory"), which is perhaps from PIE *plag- (on notion of "something extended"), variant form of root *plak- (1) "to be flat." De Vaan tentatively compares Greek plagia "sides, flanks," Old High German flah "flat," Old Saxon flaka "sole of the foot." (www.etymonline.com);

In fact, the word "plagiat" into Uzbek or Karakalpak derived from Russian "плагиат" and into Russian from English. Linguists and scientists always attempted to find out an equivalent word in both Karakalpak and uzbek, but others claim that it is more conceivable and true to use the word itself as a calque.

Instagram – eng. Instagram - the name of a social media service for taking, changing, and sharing photographs and video (dictionary.cambridge.org).

In the word Instagram -gram is noun word-forming element, "that which is written or marked," from Greek gramma "that which is drawn; a picture, a drawing; that which is written, a character, an alphabet letter, written letter, piece of writing;" in plural, "letters," also "papers, documents of any kind," also "learning," from stem of graphein "to draw or write" (see -graphy). Some words with it are from Greek compounds, others are modern formations. Alternative -gramme is a French form.

Repper – eng. Rapper - a musician who performs the type of popular music of African-American origin that features rhythmic speaking set to a strong beat (dictionary.cambridge.com)

Rapper is one who or that which raps" in any sense, 1610s; see rap (v.)). It could mean "door-knocker" (1630s), "spirit-rapper" (1755), "professional perjurer" (1840), prison slang for "prosecutor" in prison slang (1904), "itinerant antiques buyer," with a

tinge of shadiness (1914). The hip-hop performance sense emerged c. 1979. Rapster is from 1772 (www.etymonline.com);

Rep-klip – eng. Rap clip – is the first component of complex words. Denotes relatedness to rap music and there are numerous words like it in both uzbek and karakalpak such as Рэп-альбом, рэп-альянс, рэп-артист, рэп-бар, рэп-битва, рэп-группа, рэп-звёздочка, рэп-идол, рэп-идол, рэп-коллектив, рэп-команда, рэп-композиция, рэп-конкурс, рэп-культура, рэп-культура, рэп-куплеты, рэп-магнат, рэп-мир, рэп-музыка, рэп-новости, рэп-общественность, рэп-певец, рэп-песня, рэп-сборник, рэп-стиль, рэп-сцена, рэп-тарабарщина, рэп-трио, рэп-тусовка, рэп-фестиваль from English word - rap;

Bloger – eng. Blogger - someone who writes a blog (= a regular record of someone's ideas, opinions, or experiences that is put on the internet for other people to read) (dictionary.cambridge.com);

Blog , blogger (n.) - "online journal," 1998, short for weblog (which is attested from 1993 but in the sense "file containing a detailed record of each request received by a web server"), from (World Wide) Web (n.) + log (n.2). Joe Bloggs (c. 1969) was British slang for "any hypothetical person" (compare U.S. equivalent Joe Blow); earlier blog meant "a servant boy" in one of the college houses (c. 1860, see Partridge, who describes this use as a "perversion of bloke"), and, as a verb, "to defeat" in schoolboy slang. The Blogger online publishing service was launched in 1999 (www.etymonline.com);

In conclusion, having analyzed above mentioned examples, it is possible to say that the study of media news texts are being one of the actual issues in the current Linguistics and particularly, the loanwords stayed widespread among the news texts and influencing the speech of the Karakalpak and uzbek speakers in different way. Therefore, it is immeasurably pivotal to analyze each loanword that are being borrowed from different foreign languages make them closely connect to the People, society or from the sociolinguistic point of view.

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